

Synthetic, spectral, thermal and antimicrobial activity studies of some transition metal complexes derived from 2-hydroxy-methylbenzaldehyde *N*-(4'-phenyl-1',3'-thiazol-2'-yl)semicarbazone

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Abstract : The Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of Schiff base 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde *N*-(4'-phenyl-1',3'-thiazol-2'-yl)semicarbazone have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, magnetic susceptibility, UV-Visible, IR, NMR, ESR, TGA and Mass spectral data. The Schiff base behaves as tridentate ONO donor ligand and forms the complexes of the type ML stoichiometry for Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes and ML₂ (metal-ligand) stoichiometry for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, complexes and are non-electrolytic in nature. It is found that Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes exhibited tetrahedral geometry whereas Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, complexes exhibited octahedral geometry. The ligand and its complexes were tested for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*.

Keywords : Antimicrobial activity, Schiff base, semicarbazone, ESR.

Introduction

Metal complexes with potentially tridentate and tetradentate ligands have evoked much interest in coordination chemistry¹. Schiff base complexes of transition metals have played a prominent role in the development of coordination chemistry². Several Schiff base metal complexes have been studied because of their industrial and biological applications³⁻⁵. Schiff bases containing polyfunctional groups offer many practical advantages and unique structural environment for complexation⁶.

Literature survey reveals that thiazoles are well known for their varied pharmacological and antimicrobial activities⁷. In view of these findings and in continuation of our research work on coordination chemistry^{8,9}, we are reporting the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde *N*-(4'-phenyl-1',3'-thiazol-2'-yl)semicarbazone (HL) (Fig. 1) and its Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes in this communication (H refers to phenolate).

HL

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The analytical data of the synthesized ligand HL and its Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are given in Table 1. The molar conductance of all the complexes were measured in DMF at 10⁻³ M concentrations. Measured conductance values of these complexes are too low to account for their electrolytic behaviors.

IR spectra :

The band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ is observed in the ligand HL at 1601 cm⁻¹ shows a negative shift of 11-79 cm⁻¹ and appeared in the region 1590-1522 cm⁻¹ in all the com-

Table 1. Analytical, magnetic susceptibility and molar conductance data of ligand HL and its complexes

Compound/ Complex	Mol. wt.	Calcd./ (Found) (%)				Magnetic moment μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_m ($\text{cm}^2 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) Yield (%)
		M	C	H	Cl			
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$	352.41	-	61.35 (58.07)	4.58 (4.56)	-	-	-	260 (80)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	784.36	8.10 (8.01)	55.13 (54.91)	4.11 (4.05)	-	1.92	23	289 (72)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	779.51	7.53 (7.41)	55.47 (55.34)	4.14 (4.01)	-	2.92	25	248(d) (62)
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_2]$	761.73	7.74 (7.60)	56.76 (56.50)	4.11 (4.05)	7.26 (7.18)	5.01	22	253 (67)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	488.29	13.40 (12.28)	44.28 (44.10)	3.92 (3.89)	6.62 (6.58)	Dia.*	22	252(d) (53)
$[\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	535.29	21.00 (20.85)	40.48 (40.21)	3.58 (3.52)	5.69 (5.54)	Dia.*	19	>300 (67)
$[\text{Hg}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	623.47	32.17 (32.01)	34.68 (34.52)	3.07 (3.01)	13.87 (13.64)	Dia.*	22	>300 (53)

*Diamagnetic.

plexes confirms the coordination through the azomethine nitrogen atom¹⁰. In all complexes a weak band which was observed in the ligand HL at 2895 cm^{-1} has been disappeared, indicating the deprotonation of intra-molecular hydrogen bonded phenolic -OH group with azomethine nitrogen during complexation with metal ions¹⁰. A broad band appeared in the region 3496–3398 cm^{-1} in all complexes except Co^{II} indicates the presence of coordinated water or lattice water¹¹ in all these complexes. The band due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ observed in the ligand at 1673 cm^{-1} , suffers a negative shift of 9–55 cm^{-1} and appeared in the region 1664–1618 cm^{-1} in all the complexes, indicates the involvement of carbonyl oxygen in the complexation with metal ions⁸. The new bands in the complexes at 429–406 cm^{-1} and 508–460 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ respectively. The bands in the region 307–312 cm^{-1} have been assigned to M-Cl bands in the case of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes¹².

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of the ligand HL were recorded in DMF solution at 10^{-3} molar concentration. They are given in Table 3. These data are in agreement with distorted octahedral geometry¹³, octahedral geometry^{14–17} and octahedral stereochemistry¹⁸ for Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes respectively of ligand HL.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand HL :

Ligand HL showed a singlet at 2.25 ppm (3H, s) due to protons of -CH₃ group. Nine aromatic protons of thiazole and benzene rings have resonated in the region 6.75–8.25 (9H, m) as a multiplet. Two fine singlets of amide protons of -NHCONH function have appeared as distinct singlets at 10.90 (1H, s) and 9.90 (1H, s) respectively. The -OH proton of salicylaldehyde moiety has resonated

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of ligand HL and its complexes

Compound/ Complex	$\nu_{\text{NH/NH}}$	H-bonded OH	$\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$	Phenolic	$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{Cl}}$
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$	3199/3089	2895	-	1673	1601	1258	703	-	-	-	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3165/3060	-	3421	1638	1522	1285	701	429	466	-	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3165/3067	-	3428	1643	1531	1291	688	420	464	-	-
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_2]$	3148/3056	-	-	1633	1590	1280	701	417	460	-	-
$[\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3203/3105	-	3398	1618	1541	1297	695	406	465	307	-
$[\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3204/3052	-	3406	1664	1572	1273	695	407	508	310	-
$[\text{Hg}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3252/3172	-	3496	1660	1546	1272	688	419	491	312	-

Table 3. Electronic spectral data and ligand field parameters of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of ligand HL

Complex	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	Dq (cm^{-1})	B^1	β	$\beta\%$	ν_2/ν_1	LFSE (kcal mol^{-1})
[Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂].2H ₂ O	16395-13505			1479	-	-	-	-	25.37
[Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	10393	15977	20818	839	936	0.96	12.02	1.488	14.40
[Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂].2H ₂ O	9786	15023	25013	932	838	0.89	5.48	1.535	28.73

as a singlet at 11.10 (1H, s). A fine singlet at 8.40 (1H, s) is due to proton of azomethine group.

¹H NMR spectrum of Cd^{II} complex of the ligand HL :

In its ¹H NMR spectrum, a fine singlet at 2.25 (3H, s) is due to -CH₃ protons. The -OH proton of salicylaldehyde moiety which was observed at 11.10 (1H, s) in case of ligand has been disappeared indicating the involvement of phenolic oxygen in the coordination via deprotonation. The two protons of amide -NHCONH, which were appeared at 10.90 and 9.90 in case of ligand, showed a down field shift of 0.20 and 0.05 and appeared at 11.10 and 9.95 (1H, s) as two distinct singlets. The nine aromatic protons have resonated in the region 6.85-7.95 (9H, m) as a multiplet. The azomethine proton appeared at 8.40 (1H, s) in the ligand has shown a down field shift of 0.05 ppm and appeared at 8.45 ppm indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen with Cd^{II} ion.

Mass spectral analysis :

In the mass spectrum of the ligand HL, the molecular ion peak M⁺ at *m/z* 352 has not been observed, the absence of the molecular ion peak is attributed to the instability of the molecular ion formed which underwent rapid fragmentation before reaching the detector. The molecular ion by the loss of C₈H₉N₂O fragment gave a fragment ion peak A₁ at *m/z* 203. The fragment ion A₁ by the loss of hydrogen radical gave another fragment ion A₂ at *m/z* 202. Fragment ion A₂ by simultaneous expulsion of NCO and CN radicals gave another fragment ion A₃ at *m/z* 134, which is also a base peak (Scheme 1).

Magnetic susceptibility data :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were performed at room temperature (Table 1). The magnetic moment for Cu^{II} complex of the ligand HL is 1.92 B.M. The reported values for the mononuclear Cu^{II} complexes having no major spin interactions is 1.75-2.20 B.M.^{19,20}. Thus the present Cu^{II} complexes are devoid of any spin interactions with distorted octahedral geometry. In octahedral Co^{II} complexes the ground state is ⁴T_{1g} and a large orbital contribution to the magnetic moment is expected. The mixing of the singlet states

lowers the magnetic moments. The reported magnetic moment values for various Co^{II} complexes are in the range of 4.7-5.2 B.M. for octahedral complexes²¹. In the present investigation the observed magnetic moment value for Co^{II} complex is 5.01 B.M. which indicates octahedral geometry for this Co^{II} complex. For Ni^{II} complex, the observed magnetic moment value is 2.92 B.M which is in

Scheme 1

well agreement with the expected range for Ni^{II} complexes with octahedral stereochemistry (2.83–4.0 B.M)^{21,22}.

ESR spectral studies of the Cu^{II} complex of the ligand HL :

The X-band ESR spectrum of the powder Cu^{II} complex was recorded at room temperature using DPPH as a reference standard. One unpaired electron in Cu^{II} complex with ²B_{1g} as ground state lies in d_{x²-y²} orbital and follows the trend g_{||} > g_⊥ > g_e (g_e = 2.0036-free ion value). The observed g_⊥ = 2.28 and g_{||} = 2.0592 value of the Cu^{II} complex under the present study followed the same trend g_{||} > g_⊥ > g_e which suggest that the presence of unpaired electron in d_{x²-y²} orbital giving octahedral geometry²³. The observed G = 4.73 for the complex under present study evidenced the monomeric nature of the complex²⁴. This fact is further supported by the absence of a band corresponding to ΔMs = ±2 transition²⁵ in the observed ESR spectrum which is characteristic of monomeric complex.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The decomposition studies of the Co^{II} complexes have been carried out. In the thermogram of the [Co(C₁₈H₁₅N₄O₂S)₂], the loss of 2N₂ was observed at 118 °C, indicated by an inflexion in the curve at 118 °C, with weight loss of 7.468%. This practical weight loss is in accordance with the theoretical weight loss of 7.58%. The resultant intermediate complex underwent further degradation and gave another break at 305 °C with a weight loss of 8.12%, which corresponds to the expulsion of two carbon monoxide molecules and a hydrogen molecule from the above intermediate complex. The theo-

retical weight loss for this decomposition was 8.21%, agreeing well with the observed value 8.12%. The third inflection occurred at 445 °C with weight loss of 50.77%, which amounts for the weight loss of C₁₈H₁₂N₂S₂ species. This practical weight loss of 50.77% of third stage decomposition is in accordance with theoretical weight loss of 49.39%. Thereafter the compound showed a gradual decomposition upto 1000 °C and onwards. The weight of the residue corresponds to the formation of the cobalt oxide (Co₃O₄).

Antimicrobial activity :

Antimicrobial activity was carried out by the cup-plate method²⁶. The ligand HL and its Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activities at 100 μg/0.1 cm³ concentrations. The results of the antimicrobial activity with zone of inhibition have been presented in Table 4. The antibacterial activity of the ligand HL and its Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes were found to be weakly active with 11–15 mm inhibition against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, whereas Hg^{II} complex showed moderate activity with 18 mm and 19 mm inhibition against the same organisms, when compared to the standard drug Streptomycin which showed 20 mm and 22 mm inhibition against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* respectively at the same concentrations as that of the test compounds. The antifungal activity results of the ligand and its above complexes revealed that the ligand HL showed moderate activity against *A. niger* and *Candida albicans* with 17 mm and 14 mm inhibition respectively. The Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes showed good antifungal activity with 18–21 mm inhibition against both *A. niger* and *Candida*

Table 4. Antimicrobial screening data of the ligand HL and its complexes

Compound/ Complex	Antibacterial activity		Antifungal activity	
	Zone of inhibition (in mm)		Zone of inhibition (in mm)	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	11	12	17	14
[Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂].2H ₂ O	12	15	13	16
[Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂].2H ₂ O	11	13	21	20
[Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	13	13	18	17
[Zn(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl].2H ₂ O	12	13	20	21
[Cd(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl].2H ₂ O	15	13	17	16
[Hg(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl].2H ₂ O	18	19	20	22
Standard-I (Streptomycin)	20	22	-	-
Standard-II (Grisofulvin)	-	-	24	23
DMF (Control)	0	0	0	0
(Bore size)	8	8	8	8

albicans whereas Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes showed moderate activity against both *A. niger* and *Candida albicans* with 13–17 mm inhibition compared to the standard drug Grisofulvin which showed 24 mm and 23 mm inhibition against *A. niger* and *Candida albicans* respectively at the same concentrations as that of the test compounds.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals are of reagent grade. Solvents were dried and distilled before use according to standard procedures²⁷. The precursor 4-phenylthiazole-2-semicarbazide was prepared by literature method²⁸. The metal(II) salts used were in their hydrated form.

Synthesis of the ligand HL :

An equimolar mixture of 4-phenylthiazole-2-semicarbazide (0.001 mol) and 5-methylsalicylaldehyde (0.001 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) were refluxed in presence of catalytic amount of glacial acetic acid (1–2 drops) for about 6 h on a water bath. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, the separated Schiff base was collected by filtration, dried and recrystallized from absolute ethanol.

Preparation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of ligand HL :

To the hot solution of 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde *N*-(4'-phenyl-1',3'-thiazol-2'-yl)semicarbazone (HL) (0.002 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was added a hot ethanolic solution (10 ml) of respective metal(II) chloride (0.002 mol), the reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 4 h, then sodium acetate (0.5 g) was added to it and refluxed for further 2 h. It was then poured into distilled water. The resulting solid complexes were collected by filtration, washed with sufficient quantity of distilled water, then with hot ethanol to apparent dryness and dried in a vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride in a desiccator (yield 60–70%) (Table 1).

Physical measurements :

IR spectra of the synthesized ligand and its complexes were recorded as KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One FT-IR spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 400 MHz spectrometer. UV-Vis spectra of the complexes were recorded on Elico-SL 164 spectrometer in the range 200–1000 nm in DMF solution (1×10^{-3} M). Mass spectrum of ligand acquired on MASPEC system. Elemental analyses were obtained from HERAEUS

C, H, N-O rapid analyzer and metal analysis was carried out by following the standard methods. ESR measurements were carried out on a BRUKER BioSpin GmbH spectrometer working at a microwave frequency of 9.903 GHz. The experiment was carried out by using, diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) as reference with the field set at 3200 Gauss. Magnetic susceptibility were determined by the Faraday method using a model 300 Lewis coil Force Magnetometer of tesla field strength at room temperature. The instrument was calibrated with $\text{HgCo}(\text{SCN})_4$ ²⁹.

Conclusion :

In the light of above discussion we have proposed tetrahedral geometry for Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes and an octahedral geometry for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. The ligand behaves as ONO tridentate, chelating agent coordinating through the deprotonation of hydroxyl group, carbonyl group and azomethine nitrogen. The analytical data, electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibility, IR, NMR, ESR and Mass spectral data revealed mononuclear nature of the complexes. Ligands as well as its complexes were found to be less active against the bacteria *E. coli* and *S. aureus* where as moderately active against the fungi *A. niger* and *C. albicans*. All the complexes showed enhanced antimicrobial activity compared to their ligand.

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